

5.1. Characterization of the studies carried out in companies

Article Id	Company	Company size					Target	Type of location			Development methodology used				Name of the Framework	Results	Implications
		M	P	E	G	N/E		D	C	M	A	T	H	N/E			
PS1	Technology Company				X		Investigate how Psychological safety and leadership influence the accumulation of TD.			X	X				Scrum - Extreme Programming (XP)	Teams with greater psychological security, improved team collaboration and coordination.	Leaders facilitating safe work. Correct implementation of agile practices. Manage DS and DT together.
PS2	Software development company.			X			Identify the factors that generate SD in distributed ESD and propose practices to mitigate them.	X			X				Not specific	It was identified that cultural barriers, asynchronous communication and low interaction generate SD.	Manage communication through synchronous tools. Encourage social practices within the team.
PS4	Industrial company				X		Analyze the concept of architectural SD and propose a framework to manage it effectively.	X						X	Not specific	Low communication was identified as a critical architectural SD factor.	Improve communication to reduce the accumulation of SD and its effects on the architecture. Implement the DAHLIA framework that provides guidelines for identifying and managing SD.
PS5	Industrial company.			X			To study how OCs and architectural odors are related, and how they influence software quality.		X		X				Scrum	Poor interaction among team members was identified, evidenced by a lack of communication or isolation among them, which reflects negatively on the software architecture.	Properly manage social interactions among team members. Address SD and TD in a comprehensive manner.

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PS6	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X		Propose an automated tool to identify CO in open software projects.	X			X				Not specific	Anti-patterns are identified in OSS communities. The system implemented allowed us to identify isolated groups, isolated leaders with poor coordination and conflicts among team members.	Periodically monitor social interactions within the team and make corrective decisions in a timely manner.
PS7	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X		Apply statistical techniques to analyze the variability of OCs.	X						X	Not specific	They observed that OCs vary in frequency depending on the size of the team, the size of the repository and the frequency of collaboration between team members.	Prioritize efforts in the communication of team members.
PS8	Industrial company - IT services companies IS consulting firm.				X		Review and reorient the role of the software architect.			X	X				Not specific	The software architect must take an active role in social interactions with other team members.	Change the traditional perspective of the software architect in order to avoid social problems within the team. Avoid centralization of knowledge in a single team member.
PS9	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X		Analyze how social drivers (inertia, co-authorship, experience heterophily, organizational homophily) generate social debt and community smells in 13 large open-source projects	X						X	Not specific	Identifies that inertia and co-authorship strongly drive community smells, especially the "Known Devil" smell, directly linked to bug rate. Organizational homophily is less impactful.	Management of social debt should focus on modifying individual patterns. "Known Devil" can be detected automatically. Early, targeted intervention is needed in distributed communities.

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PS10	Technology company			X			Evaluate a user-story-inspired tool for capturing socio-technical debt directly from stakeholders in a large organization.				X					Debt Stories effectively capture social and technical debt, enhancing communication between roles. 83% perceive debt as frequent and risky.	Promotes early identification of debt and improves interdisciplinary communication in large technology companies.
PS11	Software Development Team in Brazil.			X			Identify how gender diversity, especially the participation of women, impacts the emergence of OCs in ESD.		X		X				Not specific	Teams with greater gender diversity, especially with female participation, show a lower frequency of OC.	Encouraging gender diversity will contribute to a favorable and participatory work environment.
PS12	Software Development Team.					X	Measure social productivity during the software development process.		X		X				Not specific	Metrics are defined to identify social productivity, frequency of interaction and the quality of communication and knowledge sharing.	Ongoing assessment of social productivity can help prevent or mitigate SD in ESDs.
PS13	Software Development Team.	X					Analyze the relationship between gender diversity in ESDs and the presence of OCs.		X			X			Not specific	Diversity contributes to greater cohesion in ESDs.	Consider gender diversity as a factor in a favorable work environment.
PS14	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X		Analyze how COs relate to the presence of bad practices in software design.	X						X	Not specific	A correlation was found between OCs and the application of poor design practices.	Improve communication and social interaction as a strategy to improve software design.
PS15	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Propose an approach based on network models that will allow more accurate detection of OC detection.	X						X	Not specific	Improve detection of absent leaders, poor coordination, bottlenecks and isolated team members.	Network metrics can be used to monitor social interactions in distributed EDS.
PS16	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Develop an approach to identify community patterns in open source projects.	X						X	Not specific	Identifying community patterns makes it possible to anticipate conflicts and plan social interventions in OSS projects.	Understand the importance of avoiding social problems to reduce isolation and miscommunication.
PS17	Undefined companies					X	Measure how TD impacts the emotional and social well-being of developers.	X						X	Not specific	The presence of TD generates feelings of anxiety and frustration in the participants, which negatively impact their motivation and performance during software development.	As a strategy to promote a good work environment, as well as the emotional and social well-being of the participants, it is essential to adequately manage TD.

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PS18	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Predicting the occurrence of OC through metrics.	X							X	Not specific	Factors such as developer experience, frequency of changes and response times were identified.	Causes can be anticipated and managed in time to minimize their impact.
PS19	Software development company.				X		Analyze how TD affects the morale and well-being of developers.	X							X	Not specific	High levels of TD and its correlation with low morale, burnout and lower job satisfaction were identified in ESDs.	Address TD not only as a technical risk, but also as a factor that directly affects the social and emotional well-being of developers.
PS20	Swedish healthcare and financial services companies.					X	Identify how social and organizational factors influence software architecture and how they affect communication, decision making and team structure.			X					X	Not specific	Deficiencies in social factors such as communication, leadership and organizational culture were identified as negatively impacting software architecture.	Architectural decisions should not be made in isolation; they should be participatory and involve team members.
PS21	Industrial company				X		Analyze how multi-team systems impact software quality and dependency management.		X			X				Not specific	60% of interactions are technical and inter-team. Lack of cross-team coordination leads to delays and quality issues	Emphasizes the need for explicit cross-team coordination and appointment of brokers for effective management in complex projects.
PS22	Software development companies.				X		Multiple case study, qualitative analysis, triangulation of interviews and artifacts			X					X	Scrum/Kanban	Analyze how power dynamics and community smells affect collaboration and organizational climate in proprietary software companies.	Power relations generate smells such as Power Distance and Priggish Members, negatively affecting motivation and coordination.
PS23	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X		To empirically test the relevance of socio-technical congruence (STMC) on software quality (bugs and churn) across 25 large open-source projects, using a formalized and operational quantitative metric (STMC).	X							X	Not specific	The study found no significant relationship between socio-technical congruence (alignment of communication and technical dependencies) and basic software quality outcomes (bugs and churn) in any temporal scenario. Other factors (such as team size and codebase size) have a much greater influence.	The findings challenge established assumptions, suggesting that focusing on optimizing communication/coordination structures for the sake of reducing bugs or churn may not be effective in large open-source environments.

																		Project resources may be better allocated to other quality drivers.
PS24	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X	Analyze the impact of cultural and geographical dispersion on the emergence of community smells in distributed teams.	X							X	Not specific	Cultural and geographical dispersion increases smells like Lone Wolf and Organizational Silo, but may mitigate others.	Recommends conscious management and measurement of diversity and dispersion to diagnose and reduce smells in distributed teams.	
PS25	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X	Provide a manually labeled dataset of developers' emotions in issue tracker comments and explore their impact on team dynamics and software processes.	X							X	Not specific	Developers express a wide range of emotions (love, joy, sadness, anger, etc.) in issue comments; emotions influence bug fixing time, project attractiveness, and social debt.	Enables affect-aware mining and research on human factors in OSS; supports further studies of emotion's role in productivity, retention, and debt.	
PS26	Technology Company				X	Explore how industry practitioners identify and address fairness debt (systematic bias) in AI-powered software, with a focus on strategies, practices, and real-world challenges.	X							X	Not specific	Professionals identify bias mainly through model output mismatches, inconsistent performance across demographics, biased training data, and algorithmic testing. They address fairness debt with data enrichment, model adjustment, crisis response, diverse team integration, and ethical/fairness review.	Highlights the need for industry guidelines on fairness debt, emphasizing both technical (data/model) and organizational (team diversity, ethics) interventions to ensure equitable AI systems. The results lay the groundwork for structured fairness debt management in practice.	
PS28	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.				X	Develop a machine learning model to predict the occurrence of OC in EDS.	X							X	Not specific	The model predicts with high accuracy the presence of social anti-patterns from socio-technical metrics.	The use of the tool can prevent SD through periodic monitoring of team interactions.	

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PS29	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Identify how social patterns in software development communities impact development processes and the quality of the final product.	X			X				Not specific	It was identified that certain social patterns are associated with the number of bugs and delays in software development.	Understanding team interaction, coordination and cooperation improves the management of human talent and technical resources.
PS30	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Improve CO detection by integrating socio-technical metrics and sentiment analysis.	X						X	Not specific	The integration of socio-technical metrics and sentiment analysis improves accuracy in identifying social interactions within OSS project repositories.	Implement more robust tools to monitor the social and emotional well-being of ESDs.
PS31	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Develop a supervised machine learning approach to detect OC in OSS repositories.	X						X	Not specific	Accurate models were achieved to identify various types of OCs from historical data.	The implementation of the model will contribute to maintaining social quality in OSS projects.
PS34	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Use genetic programming techniques to improve the emergence of OCs in collaborative software development environments	X						X	Not specific	The predictive capability of OCs was improved by Some organizational patterns were identified as promoting the emergence of OC	Implementing automated tools that Periodically review and analyze the impact of organizational structure decisions on the software development communities.
PS35	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Analyze how software development community patterns relate to the emergence of OCs in collaborative software development environments.	X						X	Not specific	Some organizational patterns were identified as promoting the emergence of OC.	Periodically review and analyze the impact of organizational structure decisions on the software development communities.
PS36	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Predict the occurrence of OC in individual developers based on sentiment analysis.	X						X	Not specific	Negative emotions were identified as leading to the occurrence of OC in EDS.	Monitoring the emotional and social well-being of developers can prevent the occurrence of OC in EDS.
PS37	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Evaluate the impact of OCs on failure prediction.	X						X	Not specific	A significant impact of social interactions on the quality of the code developed by ESDs was identified.	Identifying the root causes of SD can help improve product quality from the early stages of development.

PS38	OSS (Open Source Software) projects.					X	Analyze how the "Missing link" community odor relates to changes that introduce bugs in software development.	X						X	Not specific	It was found that isolated developers or developers with low communication tend to introduce more errors in software development.	Improving communication networks between developers can contribute to the reduction of technical errors in software projects.
PS39	Software development company.				X		Analyze the impact of SD and TD in agile projects.			X					Scrum	Poor communication and leadership practices contribute to the accumulation of TD in ESDs.	Social strategies that promote effective communication should be established in order to reduce the accumulation of TD.
PS41	Software development companies.					X	Analyze how gender diversity, in particular the inclusion of women, impacts the appearance of COs in real environments.			X	X				Non-specific.	Gender diversity correlates with lower impact on social interactions, isolation, and poor coordination and communication.	Encouraging gender diversity not only improves inclusion, but also the mental and social well-being and productivity of employees.
PS45	Industrial companies.					X	Analyze the perception and experiences of SD in real industrial environments.			X	X				Not specific	Poor coordination, communication and collaboration among team members were identified as the most frequent causes of SD.	Organizations should regularly monitor the causes that generate SD and establish effective strategies to mitigate them.

Acronyms used: M: Micro enterprise, P: Small enterprise, E: Medium enterprise, G: Large enterprise, D: Distributed team, C: Co-located team, H: Hybrid team, A: Agile framework, T: Traditional framework and N/E: not specified.